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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

D5.1 – First iDriving Prototype

Author(s):	Ioannis Tampakis, George Lalas, Dariya Rublova
Leading Partner:	Netcompany S.A.
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Report information

Purpose of the Report	This deliverable presents the first iDriving prototype, detailing components deployment, interfaces, and supporting CI/CD infrastructure. It also outlines the integration plan and milestones for testing and pilot deployments.		
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ABOUT iDriving

iDriving, a 3-year Horizon-funded project, unites 17 European partners in a mission to enhance road safety. The project focuses on transforming urban and secondary rural road infrastructure through innovation. It aligns with the EU’s goals for smart transport and actively embraces emerging technologies. Key areas of impact include enhancing driver behaviour, improving infrastructure safety, and empowering first responders. Through a comprehensive Safety Criteria Catalogue, innovative sensors, AI-based warnings, and a Digital Twin, iDriving paves the way for safer roads.

The iDriving consortium consists of the following partners:

No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	POLYTECHNEIO KRITIS	TUC	EL
3	AUSTRIATECH - GESELLSCHAFT DES BUNDES FUR AT TECHNOLOGIEPOLITISCHE MASSNAHMEN GMBH	AUSTRIATECH	AT
4	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	UNI.EIFFEL	FR
5	FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	ES
6	INGARTEK CONSULTING SL	ING	ES

7	INFRA PLAN KONZALTNIG JDOO ZA USLUGE	INFRA PLAN	HR
8	ACCELIGENCE LTD	ACCELI	CY
9	NETCOMPANY S.A.	INTRA	LU
10	SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL	SIMAVI	RO
11	ALP.Lab GmbH	ALP.LAB	AT
12	MUNICIPALITY OF ALBA IULIA	AIM	RO
13	DRAXIS RESEARCH VENTURES ASTIKI MI EL KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIRIA	DREVEN	EL
14	PRAVO I INTERNET FOUNDATION	LIF	BG
15	DIMOS THESSALONIKIS	THESSALONIKI	EL
16	GRAD KARLOVAC	COK	HR
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Glossary

Acronym/Term	Full Name
DOA	Description Of Action
IC	iDriving Component
API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
D2.3	Deliverable 2.3
DB	Database
Docker	Containerization platform
DT	Digital Twin
Git	Version Control System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoSCoW	A prioritization technique for requirements
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
RAM	Random Access Memory
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
REST	Representational State Transfer
RTSP	Real-Time Streaming Protocol
SCC	Safety Criteria Catalogue
SUMO	Simulation of Urban Mobility
T	Task
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (Drone)
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface

VMS	Variable Message Sign
VSS	Variable Speed Sign
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984
WP	Work Package
WPS	WRF Preprocessing System
WRF	Weather Research and Forecasting model
XR	Extended Reality

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the first prototype of the iDriving Unified Road Safety Ecosystem, developed within the iDriving Horizon Europe project focused on advancing road safety and infrastructure management through digital innovation. Built upon the system architecture and technical requirements established, this document describes the initial deployment of system components, their integration points, interfaces, and data exchange details.

The document provides an analysis of the deployment environment for the first prototype, clearly delineating the roles and readiness of all iDriving components across various pilot and development scenarios. It further specifies and maps the integration framework, meticulously documenting the interfaces and information flows among system modules, ensuring coherent communication and interoperability.

Moreover, this deliverable outlines the comprehensive integration plan, including its methodological framework and the necessary execution phases, designed to facilitate seamless integration and progressive validation of the entire ecosystem. A dedicated section on the Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) infrastructure elucidates the DevOps methodologies adopted, tools deployed, and workflow implementations supporting agile and robust system development. Additionally, the Message Bus implementation is described, highlighting its central role in facilitating reliable communication and data streaming between components.

The outcomes of this deliverable lay a solid foundation for subsequent activities, guiding the ongoing implementation, integration, testing, and validation processes.

1 Introduction

This deliverable gives an overview of the iDriving prototype, focusing on the details of the design and the integration and deployment process for the iDriving platform components.

As per the **DoA**, this deliverable represents the outcome of Task 5.2. Bridging Services for a Unified Road Safety Ecosystem of WP5 and takes into account the work done in Work Packages (WP) 2, 3, 4, 5 for the use cases and requirements definition (WP2) and the development of the iDriving components (WP3, WP4, WP5).

The integration process approach relies on the CI/CD and DevOps paradigm enhanced with security while the tools used are well-known and common among the technology community. This deliverable aims to define and document the following:

- Specification of corresponding components and interfaces
- Integration plan and CI/CD Platform

The software components that constitute the iDriving architecture are developed in the context of the WP3, WP4, and WP5 project working packages.

1.1 Deliverable context

Keywords	Lead Editor
Objectives	To define the system integration framework.
Work plan	<p>This deliverable focuses on the integration and validation of the iDriving prototype, specifically documenting the interface specifications, integration points, and the progressive deployment and testing of software components across the following Work Packages (WPs) and Tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP3 / T3.1 - Network Infrastructure Development and Asset Intercommunication • WP3 / T3.2 - Safety-Optimized Traffic Management Using Intelligent Algorithms for Diverse Vehicle Flows • WP3 / T3.3 - Mobile and In-Vehicle Applications for Early Warnings • WP3 / T3.4 - Aerial Surveillance in Incident Management and Maintenance Tasks • WP3 / T3.5 - Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance • WP4 / T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring • WP4 / T4.2 - AI-Powered Behavioural Analysis of Objects of Interest • WP4 / T4.3 - Visual Analysis for Identification of Maintenance Requirements • WP4 / T4.4 - Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures • WP4 / T4.5 - AI-Driven 3D Scene Generation for Safety & Maintenance Monitoring • WP5 / T5.1 - Dynamic Update of Criteria Catalogue Through Continuous Learning • WP5 / T5.2 - Bridging Services for a Unified Road Safety Ecosystem

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP5 / T5.3 - Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems • WP5 / T5.4 - Digital Twin Machine Consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies • WP5 / T5.5 - Digital Twin-Based Control Centre with XR Features for Enhanced Situational Awareness
Milestones	
Deliverables	D5.1

1.2 Document Overview

The remainder of this document is comprised of the following sections:

- **Section 2** presents the **iDriving Deployment** for the first prototype, including deployment environments for each component, as well as the status and readiness of each one.
- **Section 3** presents the **iDriving Integration Points** through a detailed mapping of interfaces between components, describing communication paths, data exchange specifications, and the interface model supporting the integration of the iDriving ecosystem.
- **Section 4** presents the **Integration Plan** by Defining the integration methodologies and execution phases, outlining the procedural framework that ensures seamless integration of the system components.
- **Section 5** presents the **iDriving CI/CD Tools and Environment**. The basic components of the CI/CD ecosystem are covered in this chapter, along with an explanation of the methodology, operating procedures, and the underlying technology that drive the development pipelines. It provides a detailed picture of the CI/CD tools, procedures, and environment used by iDriving to assist the development efforts. Creating solid DevOps concepts and deciphering the intricate inner workings of the selected CI/CD stack.
- **Section 6** presents the **iDriving Message Bus**, detailing the setup and role of the Apache Kafka-based Message Bus, which underpins reliable and scalable data streaming and inter-component communication within the iDriving architecture.
- **Section 7** presents the **Conclusion and next steps**, while summarizing the main outcomes of this deliverable.

1.3 iDriving Component Acronyms Specification

To facilitate clarity and consistency throughout this deliverable, principal components of the iDriving architecture are commonly referenced using standardized acronyms. These acronyms represent the core software tools and subsystems developed across the relevant Work Packages (WP3, WP4, WP5), and are systematically used in interface specifications, integration matrices, and deployment descriptions.

The table below provides an authoritative mapping of each component acronym to its corresponding tool or system and its association with the relevant task(s):

Acronym	Component / Tool	Associated Task
IC1	Tekniker Dataspace Connector	T3.1
IC2	Route Guidance Tool	T3.2
IC3	Signal Control Tool	T3.2
IC4	Mobile Application	T3.3
IC5	In-Vehicle Application	T3.3
IC6	Aerial Surveillance UAV System	T3.4
IC7	Autonomous UAV Deployment for Area Coverage	T3.5
IC8	Seat Belt and Cell Phone Detection Tool	T4.1
IC9	Count Cars Detection Tool	T4.1
IC10	License Plate Detection Tool	T4.1
IC11	Helmet Detection Tool	T4.1
IC12	Zebra Crossing Detection Tool	T4.1
IC13	Fallen Tree and Rockslide Detection Tool	T4.1
IC14	Crashed Vehicle Detection Tool	T4.1
IC15	Red Light Violation Detector	T4.2
IC16	Improper Lane Usage Detector	T4.2
IC17	Zebra Crossing Violation Detector	T4.2
IC18	Abrupt Movements Detector	T4.2
IC19	Pothole Detection and Severity Assessment Tool	T4.3
IC20	Weather Prediction Tool (WRF and Data Assimilation)	T4.4
IC21	AI-Based Real-Time Weather Alert System	T4.4
IC22	3D-Smart Tool	T4.5
IC23	SCC Dynamic monitoring Platform	T5.1
IC24	SUMO	T5.3
IC25	CARLA	T5.3
IC26	AI-Optimized Maintenance Through Digital Twin	T5.4
IC26.1	Dynamic Risk Assessment Tool	T5.4
IC26.2	Health and Logistics Management Tool	T5.4

IC26.3	Maintenance Scheduling Tool	T5.4
IC27	Digital Twin-Based Control Centre	T5.5

These acronyms are consistently utilized in all technical descriptions to ensure unambiguous identification of each component and to support traceability across the various work packages and tasks.

2 iDriving Deployment

2.1 Deployment – 1st Version

The deployment view provides a conceptual and physical overview of the specific pilot environments where each component of the iDriving platform is deployed. Deployment, an essential phase in the software development lifecycle, transitions the iDriving prototype from development to pilot environments, making the system accessible for validation and demonstration purposes.

Each pilot deployment scenario represents real-world conditions, allowing thorough validation of the platform's components and their interfaces. Deployment diagrams included in this section visually illustrate how individual software components are physically allocated across various nodes and environments within each pilot location. These diagrams provide stakeholders with a clear understanding of component distribution, interconnections, and integration points, ensuring effective planning, preparation, and execution of each pilot deployment.

2.1.1 Deployment Diagram

The Deployment diagram in this section provides a consolidated overview of the allocation of iDriving components across all pilot environments. The diagram below illustrates the deployment location of each software component, specifying whether it will be hosted as part of the core iDriving infrastructure, on-premises at a partner site, or within a use case dependent environment.

Although some components will not be utilized in the initial pilots, this diagram presents a consolidated view illustrating where all identified components will be deployed across the full set of pilots.

Each coloured box in the diagram represents a specific deployment location, generally aligned with an organizational boundary or partner site. Most boxes correspond to iDriving components, identified by their Task numbers. The two grey boxes within the "Use Case Dependent" outline are distinct since they represent external tools and resources (such as cameras and sensors) used in pilot scenarios, rather than core iDriving components. The central VPN symbol indicates that secure access and communication between all distributed components is managed through the project's dedicated VPN. This diagram clarifies both the organizational allocation and integration dependencies of all major system elements.

Figure 1 – Deployment diagram

2.1.2 Continuous Integration and Deployment Approach

The deployment of iDriving components leverages INTRA’s continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) methodology. This methodology facilitates efficient integration, testing, deployment, and monitoring of components within pilot environments. The utilized CI/CD pipelines, deployed on Hetzner Cloud infrastructure, ensure a secure, scalable, and streamlined deployment process.

Additional details regarding the adopted CI/CD methodology, infrastructure, and services can be found in Section 5. Even for components not following the prescribed CI/CD methodology, necessary configurations, such as networking adjustments and firewall rules, have been implemented to secure seamless data exchange among all deployed components.

2.1.3 Status of iDriving Components for 1st Prototype

This section presents a comprehensive overview of the current status of each iDriving component as of the first prototype submission. For every component, the deployment readiness, interface readiness, and additional remarks concerning development progress are explicitly documented.

Component (Acronym)	Associated Task	Ready to be Deployed? (Yes/No)	Interfaces Implemented? (Yes/No)	Additional Comments
IC1	T3.1	YES	YES	We need to clarify the data sources, data types, and communication protocols for each use case.
IC2	T3.2	YES	YES	We need calibrated SUMO models to test them.
IC3	T3.2	YES	YES	We need calibrated SUMO models to test them
IC4	T3.3	NO	NO	The first version is still in development, and it is foreseen to test the integration with the other components in the following period.
IC5	T3.3	NO	NO	The first version is still in development, and it is foreseen to test the integration with the other components in the following period.
IC6	T3.4	NO	NO	Current Status: As of today, the iDriving UAV is under construction and is expected to be ready for deployment as a standalone technology for the Plenary Meeting in France.
IC7	T3.5	Yes	Yes	First version of the tool will be ready for deployment for the first rehearsal of Nevers, France PUC. We need to define the Kafka message format for this use case.
IC8	T4.1	NO	NO	The model has already been trained, and some parts of the code have been developed. Our next step is to integrate all components to enable seatbelt and mobile phone detection, and to associate the validation with the corresponding vehicle using the tracker ID. Additionally, we need to clarify the Kafka message format for proper communication and data handling.

IC9	T4.1	NO	NO	This tool has not been implemented yet, but the output will be derived from the tracker ID aggregation. Therefore, no additional implementation is needed, the output will be generated once the detector is connected to the tracker.
IC10	T4.1	NO	NO	We have trained the model for license plate detection. The next step is to connect the detector to the license plate recognition tool to associate vehicle validation with the corresponding license plate.
IC11	T4.1	NO	NO	The model has already been trained, and some parts of the code have been deployed. We need to connect the detector with both the tracker and the license plate detection tool. Additionally, we need to define the Kafka message format for this use case.
IC12	T4.1	NO	NO	We need to train the model to detect zebra crossings and pedestrians, and connect the detector to the tracker. Additionally, we need to define the Kafka message format for this use case.
IC13	T4.1	NO	NO	A custom dataset has been created, but no further actions have been taken yet, as the specific scenarios will be addressed at a later stage
IC14	T4.1	NO	NO	A custom dataset has been created, but no further actions have been taken yet, as the specific scenarios will be addressed at a later stage
IC15	T4.2	NO	NO	We need to clarify inputs and outputs for the tool.
IC16	T4.2	NO	NO	We need to clarify inputs and outputs for the tool. However, algorithms have already been tried and tested using open-source datasets

IC17	T4.2	NO	NO	We need to clarify inputs and outputs for the tool. However, algorithms have already been tried and tested using open-source datasets.
IC18	T4.2	NO	NO	We need to clarify inputs and outputs for the tool. Still in development for the Alba Iulia UC.
IC19	T4.3	YES	NO	A primary model with core functionalities is available for initial testing and output results in JSON format. Once the interface—such as Kafka—is specified and connection details are provided, integration into the model can be swiftly completed to enable further testing.
IC20	T4.4	NO	NO	The WRF model and data assimilation with historical weather station data have been tested. Real-time input and interfacing with downstream tools are not yet implemented.
IC21	T4.4	NO	NO	The design of the alert logic is ongoing. Integration with the weather prediction tool (IC20) and other interfaces is pending development.
IC22	T4.5	YES	NO	Two primary methods have been tested and are ready to be integrated inside iDriving platform, depending on the scale of the captured scene (large/small scene)
IC23	T5.1	NO	NO	The visualization tool is ready to use with simulated data, but we need final alignment between the UC data availability, UC design, and the SCC to interface and deploy it.
IC24	T5.3	YES	NO	Currently, only one SUMO model is calibrated for UC 1.2 and ready for deployment. The other models will be deployed as soon as the data for other use cases is received, to build a calibrated SUMO network.

IC25	T5.3	NO	NO	One SUMO model has been calibrated using UC data and is ready for deployment (UC1.1). However, no data has been made available for the other use cases, preventing the development of additional calibrated SUMO networks. These models are used alongside CARLA to simulate traffic."
IC26	T5.4	NO	NO	Still in development as historical data is being collected. Simulations have already been tested.
IC26.1	T5.4	NO	NO	Still in development as historical data is being collected. Simulations have already been tested.
IC26.2	T5.4	NO	NO	Still in development as historical data is being collected.
IC26.3	T5.4	NO	NO	Still in development as historical data is being collected.
IC27	T5.5	NO	NO	The first version is still in development, and it is foreseen to test the integration with the other components in the following period.

3 iDriving Integration Points

This section presents a comprehensive overview of the integration landscape within the iDriving platform. It focuses on the definition, documentation, and verification of all communication interfaces between the platform's components. The goal is to ensure traceability, interoperability, and technical alignment throughout the development and deployment of the iDriving system.

The interfaces described in this section capture both the architectural and practical aspects of integration, providing a clear mapping between “provider” and “consumer” components, specifying the technologies and protocols employed, and giving detailed examples of exchanged data formats. This structured approach facilitates the validation, monitoring, and maintenance of the iDriving integration framework.

3.1 Interfaces

This subsection systematically documents the integration points and expected communication flows between all available components and subsystems of the iDriving platform. Following the established methodology, for each major functional area of iDriving, all component interfaces are enumerated, clearly defining the data flow across the system.

For each documented interface, the following fields are captured:

- **From-Provider:** The component or subsystem that originates the data or message.
- **To-Receiver/Consumer:** The component or subsystem that receives and processes the data.
- **Technology:** The protocol or technology used for data exchange (e.g., REST, Kafka, MQTT).
- **Description:** Concise functional overview of the interface, including what is exchanged, how, and why.

Each interface is uniquely identified according to the following syntax:

Syntax: IDRIVING__[PARTNER_NAME]_[COMPONENT_NAME]_[NUMBER]

Example: IDRIVING_INTRA_PORTAL_01

Based on the aforementioned methodology, an integration matrix was developed to identify and map all communication interfaces between iDriving components. This matrix acts as the foundational blueprint for defining the interfaces presented throughout this section. It provides a comprehensive overview of the data flows and interactions, enabling the subsequent detailed interface tables.

Given the extensive size of the integration matrix, it is not included directly within the main body of the deliverable. Instead, it is provided in Annex 1. Readers are

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referred to Annex 1 for the full integration matrix, which underpins the detailed specifications that follow.

3.1.1 T3.1. Network Infrastructure Development and Asset Intercommunication

IDRIVING: Tekniker Dataspace Connector: Network Infrastructure Development and Asset Intercommunication						
Interface #1	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_TEKNIKE R_TeknikerDatasp aceConnector_1	Every compo nent	Every compon ent but IC7	-	REST	Any data from a data source of an organization that should be controlled for its usage by a processing tool of other organization.

3.1.2 T3.2. Safety-Optimized Traffic Management Using Intelligent Algorithms for Diverse Vehicle Flows

IDRIVING: Route Guidance Tool: Safety-Optimized Traffic Management Using Intelligent Algorithms for Diverse Vehicle Flows						
Interface #2	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_MBL- TUC_RouteGuidanc e_1	IC2	IC24	No	other	Sends real-time alternative route recommendations, from the Route Guidance Tool directly to SUMO simulator using interfaces already integrated within the software.

IDRIVING: Signal Control Tool: Safety-Optimized Traffic Management Using Intelligent Algorithms for Diverse Vehicle Flows						
Interface #3	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_MBL- TUC_SignalControl _1	IC3	IC24	No	other	Traffic light splits are computed and broadcasted to the traffic lights within SUMO using interfaces already integrated within the software.

3.1.3 T3.3. Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings

IDRIVING: Mobile Application: Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings						
Interface #4	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_SI MAVI_ Mobile Application_1	IC6, IC8, IC9, IC10, IC11, IC12, IC13 IC14, IC20, IC21, IC23, IC24, IC25	IC1, IC27	Yes	REST API	Interface receives data <i>from</i> the other components, centralizes it at server level, and <i>sends data to</i> the Dataspace Connector (IC1) and to the Digital Twin-Based Control Centre (IC27), against the data schema definitions of the messages.

IDRIVING: In-Vehicle Application: Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings						
Interface #5	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_SI MAVI_ In- Vehicle Application_ 1	IC6, IC8, IC9, IC10, IC11 IC12, IC13 IC14, IC20, IC21, IC23, IC24, IC25	IC1, IC27	Yes	REST API	Interface receives data <i>from</i> the other components, centralizes it at server level, and <i>sends data to</i> the Dataspace Connector (IC1) and to the Digital Twin-Based Control Centre (IC27), against the data schema definitions of the messages.

3.1.4 T3.4. Aerial Surveillance in Incident Management and Maintenance Tasks

IDRIVING: Aerial Surveillance UAV system: Aerial Surveillance in Incident Management and Maintenance Tasks						
Interface #7	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_ACCELL_Aerial_Surveillance_UAV_System_1	IC7, IC23, IC24, IC25, IC27	IC4, IC5, IC12, IC13, IC14, IC19, IC22, IC24, IC25, IC27	Yes	e.g. REST, Kafka	The iDriving UAV will execute computations onboard using an NVIDIA processor. It will stream raw data and provide intelligence information, on the detected incidents based on onboard data processing algorithms.

3.1.5 T3.5. Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance

IDRIVING: Autonomous UAV Deployment for Area Coverage: Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance						
Interface #8	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CERT_H_Coverage_tool_1	IC7	IC6	Yes	e.g. REST, Kafka	<p>What: JSON-formatted data including UAV specifications (e.g., battery capacity, speed, camera FoV), WGS84-defined mission areas, obstacle/no-fly zone polygons, and the resulting computed flight path waypoints with relevant metadata.</p> <p>How: Data is exchanged via a Kafka message bus, with the output communicated as standardized JSON payloads</p> <p>Why: To integrate UAV mission planning capabilities into external systems by enabling seamless exchange of mission parameters and receiving optimized coverage paths for autonomous execution.</p>

3.1.6 T4.1. Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring

IDRIVING: Seat Belt and Cell Phone Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring						
Interface #9	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CERT_H_Seatbelt&MobileTool_1	IC6, Road cameras	IC4, IC5 IC23	Yes	Kafka	The tool is responsible for detecting violations in the video frame. The results may be displayed on a visualization dashboard. The violation frame will be sent to both IC4 and IC5, while metadata—such as alerts, camera location, class, track ID, etc.—will be sent to IC23.

IDRIVING: Count Cars Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring						
Interface #10	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CERT_H_CountCars_DetectionTool_1	IC6, Road cameras	IC4, IC5, IC23	Yes	Kafka	Metadata, such as the number of the cars in a frame, is sent both to IC4, IC5 and IC23.

IDRIVING: License Plate Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring						
Interface #11	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CERT_H_LicensePlateTool_1	IC6, Road cameras	IC4, IC5, IC15, IC16 IC23	Yes	Kafka	The tool detects the license plate of a car and sends the frame with each bounding box and its corresponding track ID. The ID of each license plate is sent to IC15, IC16 for cross-validation of any violation.

IDRIVING: Helmet Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring						
Interface #12	ID	From - Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CERT_H_HelmetTool_1	IC6, Road cameras	IC4, IC5 IC23	Yes	Kafka	The detected violation frame is sent to both IC4 and IC5. Metadata related to the detected objects—such as class, track ID, score—as well as alerts and the camera's location, are sent to IC23.

IDRIVING: zebra Crossing Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring						
Interface #13	ID	From - Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CERT_H_ZebraCrossingTool_1	IC6, Road cameras	IC17, IC23	Yes	Kafka	<p>After the last meeting, we concluded that we will change the detection classes in the zebra crossing scenario.</p> <p>We decided not to detect the zebra crossing itself. Instead, TEK will coordinate with the UC leaders to install static road cameras.</p> <p>Regarding Task 4.1, we agreed that only car and pedestrian classes will be detected in the zebra crossing scenario. The tool will provide the class and track ID for each detected object.</p> <p>We will create a bounding box in the frame focusing on the zebra crossing area. TEK will use the track ID of each object to determine whether a pedestrian crosses within the designated crossing zone.</p> <p>The results are sent to IC17 for cross validation of violation</p>

IDRIVING: Fallen tree and Rockslide Plate Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring

Interface #14	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CERT_H_DisasterTool_1	IC6	IC24, IC25	Yes	Kafka	<p>The detected violation frame and corresponding metadata are sent to both the IC24 and IC25 platforms.</p> <p>Metadata regarding the number of cars in the scene is sent to IC2.</p>

IDRIVING: Crashed vehicle Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring

Interface #15	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CERT_H_CrashedCarTool_1	IC6	IC18, IC24, IC25	Yes	Kafka	<p>The detected violation frame is sent to both the IC24 and IC25 platforms. Metadata is also sent to IC18 and IC3.</p>

3.1.7 T4.2. AI-Powered Behavioural analysis of objects of interest

IDRIVING: Red light violation detector

Interface #16	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_TEK_NIKER_LightViolation_1	IC6, Road Cameras	IC4, IC27, IC23	Yes	Kafka	Reporting of traffic light violation

IDRIVING: Improper lane usage detector						
Interface #17	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ImproperLaneUsage_1	IC6, Road Cameras, IC10, IC11	IC4, IC23, IC27	Yes	Kafka	Lane encroachment detection

IDRIVING: Zebra crossing violation detector						
Interface #18	ID	From -Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ZebraCrossingViolation_1	IC6, Road Cameras, IC12, IC13, IC27	IC4, IC23, IC27	Yes	Kafka	Detection of violation at pedestrian crossings

IDRIVING: Abrupt movements detector						
Interface #19	ID	From -Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_AbruptMovement_1	IC1, IC4, IC5	IC4, IC23, IC27	Yes	Kafka	Detection of sudden movements (anomalies)

3.1.8 T4.3. Visual analysis for Identification of Maintenance Requirements

IDRIVING: Pothole Detection and Severity Assessment Tool: Visual analysis for Identification of Maintenance Requirements

Interface #20	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CERTH_DDSA_1	IC1, IC6, IC22 Additionally, input is expected in the form of videos—either RTSP streams or offline MP4 files—as well as JPEG images from the pilot provider, accompanied by any available metadata such as GPS coordinates. These inputs, which may originate from road surveillance	IC1, IC22, IC23, IC26, IC27	Yes	Kafka	The detected road defects and severity from the images are transmitted in JSON format via Kafka. For annotated images or video outputs, the file storage path on the iDriving server is shared through Kafka as well.

		cameras, are not linked to any specific task.				
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3.1.9 T4.4. Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures

IDRIVING: Weather Prediction Tool (WRF and Data Assimilation): Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures

Interface #21	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_DRE_VEN_WeatherPredictTool_1	Open-Source Global Weather Models, Weather stations from Pilots	IC21, IC26.1, IC26.2, IC26.3, IC27	No	File system, REST API	The data sent consists of gridded and time-series weather forecast outputs in NetCDF format. The forecasts are generated by the WRF model using ECMWF data and are enhanced through data assimilation of ground-based observations from weather stations in the pilot areas.

IDRIVING: AI-Based Real-Time Weather Alert System: Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures

Interface #22	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_DRE_VEN_AIAIAlerts_1	IC20, IC26,2	IC4, IC5, IC26.1, IC26.2, IC26.3, IC27	Yes	REST API	This AI tool generates real-time forecast weather alerts based on data from the weather prediction tool. It uses input from the WRF model, weather stations, and forecast data to

						detect hazardous conditions and immediately communicates alerts to the iDriving ecosystem.
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3.1.10 T4.5. AI-driven 3D Scene Generation for Safety & Maintenance Monitoring

IDRIVING: 3D-Smart Tool: AI-driven 3D Scene Generation for Safety & Maintenance Monitoring						
Interface #23	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_CER TH_3DSMART_ Tool_1	IC1, IC6, IC19	IC1, IC19, IC26, IC27	Yes	Kafka	<p>There are two different implementations for 3D reconstruction, depending on the scale of the scene. In both cases the tool receives the video or sequential images via Kafka.</p> <p>Small scale scenes: for real-time rendering the 3D results are visualized using built-in viewer, which runs on a localhost accessible via a web browser at a URL like http://localhost:7007.</p> <p>Also, there is an option to render videos or export 3D models in .ply format which can be used later to external 3d engines (e.g. unity, blender). This URL or video/ .ply file path will be transmitted via Kafka.</p> <p>Large scale scenes: the 3D results are visualized using built-in compiled binary app.</p>

3.1.11 T5.1. Dynamic Update of Criteria Catalogue Through Continuous Learning

IDRIVING: Dynamic Update of Criteria Catalogue Through Continuous Learning						
Interface #24	ID	From - Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_UNI.EIFFEL_VIZTool_1	IC8, IC9, IC11, IC12, IC13, IC14, IC15, IC16, IC17, IC18	IC23	Yes	REST	This tool is designed to process input data from IDRIVING and UC to compute the KPIs defined in the SCC. It is a Python-based system that computes data and provides a visualization interface through a web application frontend. It also aims to enable continuous learning of KPIs to alert operators and support the evaluation of KPI measurements.

3.1.12 T5.3. Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems

IDRIVING: SUMO: Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems						
Interface #25	ID	From -Provider	To - Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_UNI.EIFFEL_DIGITALTWIN_1	IC2, IC3, IC13, IC14, IC15, IC16, IC17, IC18	IC4, IC5	Yes	REST	It provides safety alerts and measures through a traffic simulator powered by real sensor data. The simulator aims to recreate traffic scenarios trained on historical traffic data at various scales, while considering real monitored events.

IDRIVING: CARLA: Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems						
Interface #26	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_UNI.EIFFEL_DIGITALTWIN_2	IC13, IC14, IC15, IC16, IC17, IC18	IC4, IC5	Yes	REST	Providing safety measures and alerts at the intersection level by running a simulation based on real-time traffic monitoring along the edges.

3.1.13 T5.4. Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies

IDRIVING: AI-Optimized Maintenance Through Digital Twin: Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies						
Interface #27	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_AI_Optimized_Maintenance_1	IC9, IC19, IC20	IC27 (Control centre)	Yes	REST API	Interface for sending processed maintenance planning and risk evaluation data to the control centre for visualization and integration with operational systems

IDRIVING: Dynamic Risk Assessment Tool: Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies						
Interface #28	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_Dynamic_Risk_Assessment_1	IC26.1	IC27	Yes	REST API	Computes and sends risk level assessments to the Control Centre based on internal logic.

IDRIVING: Health And logistics Management Tool: Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies

Interface #29	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_TEK_NIKER_Health_Logistics_1	IC9, IC19	IC27	Yes	REST API	Receives traffic flow data from the Car Counting Tool (IC9) and pavement damage information from the Pothole Detection Tool (IC19) to assess asset health and coordinate logistics. Outputs health status and logistical considerations to the Control Centre.

IDRIVING: Maintenance Scheduling Tool: Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies

Interface #30	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_TEK_NIKER_Maintenance_Scheduling_1	IC10, IC21	IC27	Yes	REST API	Uses traffic condition data from the Car Counting Tool (IC9) and weather forecasts from the Weather Prediction Tool (IC20) to generate optimized maintenance schedules. These schedules are sent to the Control Centre for execution planning.

3.1.14 T5.5. Digital Twin-Based Control Centre with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness

IDRIVING: Digital Twin-Based Control Centre: Digital Twin-Based Control Centre with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness						
Interface #31	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_SIMA_VI_Digital_Twin_Based_Control_Centre_1	IC6, IC15, IC16, IC17 IC18, IC20, IC21, IC22, IC23, IC24, IC25, IC26 IC26.2, IC26.3	IC27	Yes	REST API	Interface for inbound data acts as the single point for all data <i>received from</i> the other components and centralized at server level against the data schema definitions of the messages.

IDRIVING: Digital Twin-Based Control Centre: Digital Twin-Based Control Centre with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness						
Interface #32	ID	From -Provider	To – Receiver / Consumer	Mediated via IC1 (Yes/No)	Technology	Description
	IDRIVING_SIMA_VI_Digital_Twin_Based_Control_Centre_2	IC27	IC1, IC4, IC5	Yes	REST API	Interface for outbound data acts as the single point for all data <i>sent to</i> the Mobile/In-vehicle applications (IC4, IC5) and Dataspace Connector (IC1) components, against the data schema definitions of the messages.

3.2 Data Formats Per Interface

For each interface defined above, this subsection provides:

- **The data format specification** (e.g., JSON schema, REST payload, Protocol Buffers).
- **An example of the actual data payload** as transmitted over the interface.

This ensures that all integration points are both technically and semantically aligned, reducing ambiguity and supporting efficient development and troubleshooting.

Interface ID	Data Format	Example Payload
IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_TeknikerDataspaceConnector_1	JSON	Not Applicable
IDRIVING_MBL-TUC_RouteGuidance_1	other	Internal functional calls within SUMO
IDRIVING_MBL-TUC_SignalControl_1	other	Internal functional calls within SUMO
IDRIVING_Mobile_Application_1	JSON via REST API	<pre>{ "header": { "sentUTC": "2025-07-18T10:00:55Z", "recipients": "SIMAVI", "msgIdentifier": "63c914d76df4af00017011f5" }, "body": { "events": [{ "uid": "63c913926df4af0001701135", "creationTime": "2025-07-18T10:00:55Z", "coordinates": { "x": 100.0, "y": -50.0 }, "eventText": "Lane violation detected", "eventType": "" }] } }</pre>

		<pre> }] } } </pre>
IDRIVING_In-Vehicle_Application_1	JSON via REST API	<pre> { "header": { "sentUTC": "2025-07-18T10:00:55Z", "recipients": "SIMAVI", "msgIdentifier": "63c914d76df4af00017011f5" }, "body": { "events": [{ "uid": "63c913926df4af0001701135", "creationTime": "2025-07-18T10:00:55Z", "coordinates": { "x": 100.0, "y": -50.0 }, "eventText": "Lane violation detected", "eventType": "" }] } } </pre>
IDRIVING_ACCELIAerial_Surveillance_UAV_System_1	Jpeg, mp4	Camera Payload: Siyi A8 mini
IDRIVING_CERTH_Coverage_tool_1	JSON via Kafka	<pre> { "header": { "sender": "CERTH_Path_Planning", "sentUTC": "24-02-2022 11:33:14", "topicName": "TOPIC_NAME" }, "body": { "name": "PathPlanner", "time": "24-02-2022 11:33:14", "type": "IDRIVINGWaypointMissions", "locationUnit": "latlong", "speed": 2, "missions": [{ "name": "Mission", "typeID": </pre>

		<pre>"WaypointMission", "waypoints": [{ "altitude": 50, "heading": 0, "latitude": 40.63788629706725, "gimbal_pitch": -87, "longitude": 22.91111564651211 }, { "altitude": 50, "heading": 0, "latitude": 40.63985895239085, "gimbal_pitch": -87, "longitude": 22.91135596776301 }]] }</pre>
IDRIVING_CERTH_Seatbelt&MobileTool_1	JSON via Kafka	<pre>{ "records": [{ "value": { "header": { "topicName": "ObjectDetection", "msgIdentifier": "2", "cameraID": 666, "sentUTC": "2025-07-01T10:28:13.401107Z", "district": "Graz", "body": { "detection_list": [{ "frameID": 3, "CountVehicles": 1, "imageURL": "https://3ab7-2a02-214c-8861- d100-f641-2d04-160e-c490.ngrok- free.app/images/frame_0003.jpg", "detections": [{ "objectID": 1, "class": "seatbelt", "confidence": 0.6025731563568115, "bbox": [450.198974609375, 95.11743927001953, 560.0056762695312, 140.77142333984375], }] }] } } } }] }</pre>

		<pre>{ "objectID": 2, "class": "mobile", "confidence": 0.5723400712013245, "bbox": [639.8908081054688, 77.97142791748047, 765.962646484375, 131.5926971435547], }] }] } }] } } }]</pre>
IDRIVING_CERTH_CountCars_DetectionTool_1	JSON via Kafka	<p>Count cars is a key value in the body of the message</p> <p>.....</p> <pre>"body": { detection_list": [{ "frameID": 3, "CountCars": 1, "imageUrl": "https://3ab7-2a02-214c-8861-d100-f641-2d04-160e-c490.ngrok-free.app/images/frame_0003.jpg", }] }</pre> <p>.....</p>
IDRIVING_CERTH_LicensePlateTool_1	JSON via Kafka	<pre>{</pre>

		<pre>"image_id": 1, "frame": 4, "bbox": [2201.220703125, 1167.220703125, 2783.32958984375, 1740.07421875], "plate_coords": [2416.89697265625, 1575.8836669921875, 2584.824462890625, 1628.0635986328125], "detection_confidence": 0.585705996, "license_plate": "NV51VSU", "ocr_confidence": 0.54740798 }</pre>
IDRIVING_CERTH_3D_Smart_Tool_1	JSON via Kafka	<pre>{ "3D_url": http://localhost:7007 }</pre>
IDRIVING_CERTH_HelmetTool_1	JSON via Kafka	<pre>{ "records": [{ "value": { "header": { "topicName": "ObjectDetection", "msgIdentifier": "2", "cameraID": 666, "sentUTC": "2025-07-01T10:28:13.401107Z", "district": "Nevers", "body": { "detection_list": [{ "frameID": 3, "CountVehicles": 1, "imageURL": "https://3ab7-2a02-214c-8861-d100-f641-2d04-160e-c490.ngrok-free.app/images/frame_0003.jpg",</pre>

		<pre> "detections": [{ "objectID": 1, "class": "helmet", "confidence": 0.6025731563568115, "bbox": [450.198974609375, 95.11743927001953, 560.0056762695312, 140.77142333984375], }, { "objectID": 2, "class": "no-helmet", "confidence": 0.5723400712013245, "bbox": [639.8908081054688, 77.97142791748047, 765.962646484375, 131.592697143554], }] } </pre>
IDRIVING_CERTH_ZebraCrossingTool_1	JSON via Kafka	<pre> { "records": [{ </pre>

		<pre> "value": { "header": { "topicName": "ObjectDetection", "msgIdentifier": "2", "cameraID": 666, "sentUTC": "2025-07-01T10:28:13.401107Z", "district": "Nevers", "body": { "detection_list": [{ "frameID": 3, "imageURL": "https://3ab7-2a02-214c-8861-d100-f641-2d04-160e-c490.ngrok-free.app/images/frame_0003.jpg", "detections": [{ "objectID": 1, "class": "Pedestrian", "confidence": 0.6025731563568115, "bbox": [450.198974609375, 95.11743927001953, 560.0056762695312, 140.77142333984375], }, { "objectID": 2, "class": "Cyclist", "confidence": 0.5723400712013245, "bbox": [639.8908081054688, 77.97142791748047, 765.962646484375, </pre>
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IDRIVING_CERTH_CrashedCarTool_1	JSON via Kafka	<pre>{ "records": [{ "value": { "header": { "topicName": "ObjectDetection", "msgIdentifier": "5", "uav_status": "Flying", "droneID": 666, "drone_name": "Test_1", "sentUTC": "2025-07-01T10:28:16.858040Z", "district": "Spain", "body": { "detection_list": [{ "frameID": 12, "imageURL": "https://3ab7-2a02-214c-8861-d100-f641-2d04-160e-c490.ngrok-free.app/images/frame_0012.jpg", "detections": [{ "objectID": 1, "class": "crashed-car", "confidence": 0.6025731563568115, "bbox": [450.198974609375, 95.11743927001953, 560.0056762695312, 140.77142333984375], "obj_geolocation": [37.96571531572335, 23.742635883143407] }] }, "GeoLocation": { "latitude": 37.965631, "longitude": 23.74234552, "altitude": 100 } } } } }] }</pre>
IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_LightViolation_1	JSON	<p>TDB - the following structure represents an initial shared format across multiple IDs (IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_LightViolation_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ImproperLineUsage_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ZebraCrossingViolation_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_AbruptMovement_1). Each detected object may include a "violations" field as shown below:</p> <pre>{ "records": [{ "value": { "header": { "topicName": "ObjDet", "msgIdentifier": "xxx", "sender": "CERTH_OBJ", "recipients": "xxx",</pre>

		<pre> "sentUTC": "2024-11-01T15:44:49.276766Z", "district": "Chania" }, "body": { "detection_list": [{ "frameID": "12", "detections": [{ "objectID": 1, "class": "car", "confidence": 0.91, "bbox": { "x_min": "350", "y_min": "220", "x_max": "460", "y_max": "360" }, "violations": ["red_light_violation"] }, { "objectID": 2, "class": "pedestrian", "confidence": 0.80, "bbox": { "x_min": "600", "y_min": "190", "x_max": "630", "y_max": "310" } }] }] } </pre>
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		<pre> }, "violations": ["jaywalking"] }] }] } } } }] } </pre>
IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ImproperLineUsage_1	JSON	<p>interface IDs</p> <p>(IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_LightViolation_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ImproperLineUsage_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ZebraCrossingViolation_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_AbruptMovement_1).</p> <p>Each detected object may include a "violations" field as shown below:</p> <pre> { "records": [{ "value": { "header": { "topicName": "ObjDet", "msgIdentifier": "xxx", "sender": "CERTH_OBJ", "recipients": "xxx", "sentUTC": "2024-11-01T15:44:49.276766Z", "district": "Chania" } } }], </pre>

		<pre>"body": { "detection_list": [{ "frameID": "12", "detections": [{ "objectID": 1, "class": "car", "confidence": 0.91, "bbox": { "x_min": "350", "y_min": "220", "x_max": "460", "y_max": "360" }, "violations": ["improper lane usage"] }, { "objectID": 2, "class": "pedestrian", "confidence": 0.80, "bbox": { "x_min": "600", "y_min": "190", "x_max": "630", "y_max": "310" }, "violations": ["jaywalking"] }] }] }</pre>
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		<pre> }] } } }] } </pre>
<p>IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ZebraCrossingViolation_1</p>	<p>JSON</p>	<p>interface IDs</p> <p>(IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_LightViolation_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ImproperLineUsage_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ZebraCrossingViolation_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_AbruptMovement_1).</p> <p>Each detected object may include a "violations" field as shown below:</p> <pre> { "records": [{ "value": { "header": { "topicName": "ObjDet", "msgIdentifier": "xxx", "sender": "CERTH_OBJ", "recipients": "xxx", "sentUTC": "2024-11-01T15:44:49.276766Z", "district": "Chania" }, "body": { "detection_list": [{ "frameID": "12", "detections": [</pre>

		<pre>{ "objectID": 1, "class": "car", "confidence": 0.91, "bbox": { "x_min": "350", "y_min": "220", "x_max": "460", "y_max": "360" }, "violations": ["red_light_violation"] }, { "objectID": 2, "class": "pedestrian", "confidence": 0.80, "bbox": { "x_min": "600", "y_min": "190", "x_max": "630", "y_max": "310" }, "violations": ["jaywalking"] }] } }</pre>
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		<pre>] }</pre>
IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_Abrupt Movement_1	JSON	<p>interface IDs (IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_LightViolation_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ImproperLineUsage_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_ZebraCrossingViolation_1, IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_AbruptMovement_1). Each detected object may include a "violations" field as shown below:</p> <pre>{ "records": [{ "value": { "header": { "topicName": "ObjDet", "msgIdentifier": "xxx", "sender": "CERTH_OBJ", "recipients": "xxx", "sentUTC": "2024-11-01T15:44:49.276766Z", "district": "Chania" }, "body": { "detection_list": [{ "frameID": "12", "detections": [{ "objectID": 1, "class": "car", "confidence": 0.91, "bbox": {</pre>

		<pre> "x_min": "350", "y_min": "220", "x_max": "460", "y_max": "360" }, "violations": ["abrupt_stop"] }, { "objectID": 2, "class": "car", "confidence": 0.80, "bbox": { "x_min": "600", "y_min": "190", "x_max": "630", "y_max": "310" }, "violations": ["high_acceleration"] }] }] } }] } </pre>
IDRIVING_CERTH_DDSDA_1	JSON via Kafka	<pre> { "frame_id": 1, "total_detections": 3, </pre>

		<pre> "class_counts": { "crack": 2, "pothole": 1 }, "detections": [{ "frame_id": 451, "bbox": [1014.3402709960938, 826.01513671875, 1148.533935546875, 1077.636962890625], "confidence": 0.4907393455505371, "class_id": 0, "class_name": "crack", "track_id": 553 }, { "frame_id": 451, "bbox": [631.1109619140625, 804.3102416992188, 813.7369995117188, 931.8670043945312], "confidence": 0.2995196580886841, "class_id": 0, "class_name": "crack", "track_id": 556 }, { "frame_id": 451, </pre>
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		<pre>"bbox": [868.3612670898438, 746.6318969726562, 901.3302612304688, 808.5069580078125], "confidence": 0.3786379098892212, "class_id": 1, "class_name": "pothole", "track_id": 580 }</pre>
IDRIVING_DREVEN_Weather PredictTool_1	NetCDF (.nc) for model outputs; CSV for observed station data	<p>NetCDF: wrfout_d01_20250710_00:00:00.nc</p> <p>CSV: File.csv station_id,latitude,longitude,timestamp,temperature,wind_speed,rh</p>
IDRIVING_DREVEN_AIAAlerts_1	JSON via REST API	<pre>{ "locations": { "location_name_1": { "pedestrian": { "now": "...", "now+3": "...", "now+6": "..."}, "vehicles": { "now": "...", "now+3": "...", "now+6": "..."} }, "location_name_2": { "pedestrian": { "now": "...", "now+3": "...", "now+6": "..."}, "vehicles": { "now": "...", "now+3": "...", "now+6": "..."} }, ... }, "timestamp": "...", "alert_type": "...", "source": "AIWeatherAlertSystem" }</pre>
IDRIVING_CERTH_3DSMART_Tool_1	JSON via Kafka	<pre>{ "url": http://localhost:7007/ }</pre>
IDRIVING_UNI.EIFFEL_VIZTool_1	JSON via REST API	<pre>{ "time": 2025-07-18T10:00:55Z "duration_time": 300, "road_data": { "road_ID": { "lanes": 1, "kpi_name": [0, 0], "flow_out": [0, 0], "avg_speed": [0, 0], "std_speed": [NaN, NaN],</pre>

IDRIVING_UNI.EIFFEL_DIGITALTWIN_1	JSON via REST API	{ "time": 2025-07-18T10:00:55Z, "Safety_alert_1": [{ "value": 0.3000000000000000004, "type":"zebra_crossing", "location": [64.14453792982009, 42.723729067750185], "road_user": "veh", "road_id": "31306486#0" },
IDRIVING_UNI.EIFFEL_DIGITALTWIN_2	JSON via REST API	{ "time": 2025-07-18T10:00:55Z, "Safety_alert_1": [{ "value": 0.3000000000000000004, "type":"zebra_crossing", "location": [64.14453792982009, 42.723729067750185], "road_user": "veh", "road_id": "31306486#0" },
IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_Dynamic_Risk_Assessment_1	TBD	TBD
IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_Health_Logistics_1	TBD	TBD
IDRIVING_TEKNIKER_Maintenance_Scheduling_1	TBD	TBD
IDRIVING_SIMAVI_Digital_Twin_Based_Control_Centre_1	JSON via REST API	{ "header": { "sentUTC": "2025-07-18T10:00:55Z", "recipients": "SIMAVI", "msgIdentifier": "63c914d76df4af00017011f5" }, "body": { "events": [{ "uid": "63c913926df4af0001701135", "creationTime": "2025-07-18T10:00:55Z", "coordinates": { "x": 100.0, "y": -50.0 } },

		<pre> violation "eventText": "Lane detected", "eventType": "" }] } </pre>
IDRIVING_SIMAVI_ Digital_Twin_Based_Control_Centre_2	JSON via REST API	<pre> { "header": { "sentUTC": "2025-07-18T10:00:55Z", "recipients": "SIMAVI", "msgIdentifier": "63c914d76df4af00017011f5" }, "body": { "events": [{ "uid": "63c913926df4af0001701135", "creationTime": "2025-07-18T10:00:55Z", "coordinates": { "x": 100.0, "y": -50.0 }, "eventText": "Lane violation detected", "eventType": "" }] } } </pre>

3.3 Advantages of the Interface Specification Design

The detailed enumeration and specification of all system interfaces, as presented in the preceding tables, creates a robust foundation for traceable and maintainable system integration. By adopting a standardized methodology for interface identification and documentation, seamless interoperability is ensured across a diverse set of components and partner organizations.

This design approach has several advantages:

- **Traceability and Alignment:** Every data flow is unambiguously linked to specific work package tasks, components, greatly facilitating auditability, quality assurance, and compliance verification throughout the project lifecycle.
- **Interoperability:** Standardized interface specifications, with explicit technology and payload definitions, enable components developed independently by different partners to interact reliably, reducing the risk of integration errors and communication mismatches.
- **Scalability and Extensibility:** The modular nature of the integration tables allows for straightforward addition, refinement, or replacement of system components and interfaces as the platform evolves, supporting future prototypes and deployment scenarios.
- **Efficiency in Testing and Maintenance:** Clearly defined interfaces and example payloads enable automated integration testing, efficient debugging, and streamlined onboarding of new partners or components.
- **Transparency:** The integration matrix and tables provide a holistic view of system interconnections, ensuring all partners have a shared understanding of data flows and dependencies.

Overall, this disciplined interface design and documentation process significantly reduces integration risk, forming the backbone of the iDriving ecosystem's flexibility, reliability and sustainability.

4 Integration Plan

This chapter outlines the key points and milestones for the successful execution of the integration plan. These milestones are crucial to ensure the seamless integration of the iDriving components and the exchange of data between them. The work to be performed will ensure the proper functionality of each component and will facilitate the smooth transferring of the iDriving systems from the testing labs to the trial environments.

4.1 Integration Methodologies and Phases

The integration methodology adopted for the iDriving project consists of clearly defined phases, each designed to systematically progress the integration activities and validate component interoperability.

• Planning and Organization

Initially, detailed project planning and architectural specifications are established to define the technical foundation and organize collaborative efforts among partners. This phase ensures clarity on integration objectives, roles, and responsibilities.

• Development and Bug-Fixing

This phase encompasses iterative development efforts focused on fulfilling the project's functional specifications. Developers engage in component implementation, rigorous internal testing, and continuous resolution of identified issues to maintain adherence to agreed interfaces and functionalities.

• Integration Testing

Integration tests will be conducted to verify system interoperability and validate data exchanges across components. Testing sessions will focus on generic end-to-end connectivity as well as targeted validation specific to individual Pilot Use Cases (PUCs). This stage confirms component readiness for subsequent deployment phases.

• Pilot Deployment

Upon successful integration tests, pilot deployment phases systematically roll out validated components into pilot environments. Each pilot launch represents a critical milestone, demonstrating the functional readiness and real-world applicability of the integrated components.

• Refinement and Stabilization

Continuous refinement and iterative bug-fixing are undertaken post-deployment to ensure system stability, optimize performance, and enhance reliability based on

real-world feedback. This iterative process enables improvements aligned with evolving pilot requirements.

• Prototype Milestones

Key deliverables, referred to as Prototype Milestones (D5.1, D5.4, D5.5), mark achievements in component integration and functionality. These milestones act as checkpoints to consolidate project developments and demonstrate tangible progress.

This methodical approach ensures that the integration process is visible and well-organized. It makes it easier for integrated components to be developed, tested, and deployed, ensuring that they work together effectively to accomplish the project's goals.

4.2 Integration Plan Execution

The execution of the integration plan is described in this part, including all intermediate phases and benchmarks that are essential to overseeing the project's testing and pilot demonstration operations. As the primary partner in the integration process, INTRA carefully crafted a plan while incorporating feedback from the technical partners. The following conclusions are drawn from the plan's identification of the crucial integration points:

- a. **Close Development Monitoring:** Align development activities with the components' plan to ensure synchronization.
- b. **Deployment Options Definition:** Establish appropriate testing environments and define and finalise deployment options for integration tests.
- c. **Data Flows Finalisation:** To ensure efficient data transfer, complete data flows for each iDriving component.
- d. **Completing Data Models:** To guarantee accuracy and integrity, provide thorough data models for communications that are sent.
- e. **Confirmation of Communication Interface and Protocol:** To guarantee efficient data interchange and component interactions, decide on and finalise communication interfaces and protocols.
- f. **Ongoing Technical Partner Communication:** To quickly resolve any possible problems, keep lines of communication open and efficient between technical partners.

In addition, specific plans have been carefully designed for every demonstrative milestone to optimize workflows and guarantee successful implementation. Table 1 below provides an overview of the integration plan's original design in accordance with project milestones and releases.

Table 1 - Integration Plan

Period	Milestone	Phase	Description
M1-M9	–	Planning & Organising	Initial project planning, architecture definition and team setup
M10-M14	–	Dev & Bug-Fixing	Ongoing development and issue resolution up to D5.1
M12-M13	–	Integration Testing (Deployment & Connectivity)	Generic end-to-end integration tests ahead of D5.1
M14	D5.1	Prototype Milestone	Deliver first iDriving prototype (D5.1)
M14-M19	–	Dev & Bug-Fixing	Continued dev and fixes from D5.1 through PUC 1.2
M16-M19	–	Integration Testing (PUC 1.1 Specific)	PUC 1.1 use-case connectivity & data-flow validation
M17-M18	–	Integration Testing (PUC 1.2 Specific)	PUC 1.2 use-case connectivity & data-flow validation
M19	PUC 1.2	Pilot Launch	Roll out Pilot Use Case 1.2
M19-M20	–	Dev & Bug-Fixing	Stabilization between PUC 1.2 and PUC 1.1
M20	PUC 1.1	Pilot Launch	Roll out Pilot Use Case 1.1
M20-M22	–	Dev & Bug-Fixing	Continued improvements between PUC 1.1 and PUC 2.1
M20-M21	–	Integration Testing (PUC 2.1 Specific)	PUC 2.1 use-case connectivity & data-flow validation
M22	PUC 2.1	Pilot Launch	Roll out Pilot Use Case 2.1
M22-M26	–	Dev & Bug-Fixing	Refinements between PUC 2.1 and prototype D5.4
M24-M25	–	Integration Testing (Deployment & Connectivity)	Generic end-to-end integration tests ahead of D5.4
M26	D5.4	Prototype Milestone	Deliver second iDriving prototype (D5.4)
M26-M28	–	Dev & Bug-Fixing	Iterative fixes between D5.4 and PUC 2.2

M26– M27	–	Integration Testing (PUC 2.2 Specific)	PUC 2.2 use-case connectivity & data-flow validation
M28	PUC 2.2	Pilot Launch	Roll out Pilot Use Case 2.2
M28– M31	–	Dev & Bug-Fixing	Iterative bug-fixing between PUC 2.2 and PUC 3.1
M29– M30	–	Integration Testing (PUC 3.1 Specific)	PUC 3.1 use-case connectivity & data-flow validation
M31	PUC 3.1	Pilot Launch	Roll out Pilot Use Case 3.1
M31– M33	–	Dev & Bug-Fixing	Final refinements between PUC 3.1 and PUC 3.2
M31– M32	–	Integration Testing (PUC 3.2 Specific)	PUC 3.2 use-case connectivity & data-flow validation
M32– M33	–	Integration Testing (Deployment & Connectivity)	Generic end-to-end integration tests ahead of D5.5
M33	PUC 3.2	Pilot Launch	Roll out Pilot Use Case 3.2
M33– M34	–	Dev & Bug-Fixing	Last-minute adjustments before D5.5
M34	D5.5	Prototype Milestone	Deliver final iDriving prototype (D5.5)

The outlined phases and milestones provide a structured pathway for the integration process. Beyond the execution of these tasks, it is equally important to evaluate their effectiveness. For this reason, the success of the integration activities will be assessed against Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in collaboration with WP6. These KPIs will cover scenario outcomes, tool validation, and platform efficiency. While the detailed KPI specifics will be documented separately, they will serve as important criteria during integration testing and pilot deployment phases.

5 iDriving CI/CD Tools and Environment

Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) methods must be seamlessly integrated to ensure efficiency, dependability, and agility in the production of high-quality software products in today's software development environment.

This chapter describes the fundamental elements of our CI/CD ecosystem, explaining our approach, procedures, and the underlying technologies that power our development pipelines. This thorough investigation attempts to detail iDRIVING's CI/CD tools, processes, and the environment that supports our development activities. From developing strong DevOps principles to clarifying the complex inner workings of our CI/CD stack.

5.1 Methodology - DevOps and CI/CD practices

The methodology followed in the context of iDRIVING integration is presented in this section. As the name implies, continuous integration (CI) enables frequent code integration and versioning in addition to ongoing check-ins and code verifications. This will enable the successfully included components to be integrated smoothly and, above all, validated and tested to make sure that fresh, working commits will be integrated into an application or environment that is already error-free. CI reduces the length of the release cycle, gives developers more time for development and integration, and enables them to find and address errors early on, preventing backtracking and code validation (1).

Continuous Delivery is the next stage of the CI/CD pipeline, at this point, the application's "packaging" is checked to make sure it is prepared for delivery to end customers. In addition, technologies that automate the building and release of the application are implemented at this phase, guaranteeing that the software artifacts are constantly prepared for deployment. Continual Delivery guarantees that the application can be released accurately and more frequently, even in the event of small-scale code modifications.

The last phase of the CI/CD process, Continuous Deployment, offers automated application distribution and launch. A new deliverable, output, or version is issued for each change that has made it beyond the previous steps and therefore may be incorporated into the final product; if a test along the pipeline fails, the change is not allowed to be deployed. Since this procedure is entirely automated, no human involvement is necessary.

All things considered, the CI, CD, and Continuous Deployment phases mentioned above represent the best Development and Operations approaches. To achieve the necessary quality and business objectives, this method places a strong emphasis on fostering improved and ongoing collaboration and communication between the development and operating teams. The environment and procedures that have

been covered make it easier to automate significant development, testing, and deployment-related components.

In the context of the iDRIVING Project, a group of open-source services has been developed and deployed creating a CI/CD platform giving the opportunity to the developing teams the provided tools, to commit changes, build and test source code and deploy their modules aligned with the procedures of CI/CD methodology.

5.2 CI/CD Stack Overview

The iDRIVING Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment platform provides the following features:

- A remotely accessed, distributed virtual environment, allowing for easy horizontal scaling of the platform resource-wise.
- Support for multiple, concurrent, and multi-branch environments. Branches are protected from irreversible modification by preventing forceful actions (force push, delete) and allowing role-based access.
- Automatic initiation of the build/test/deploy pipeline triggered by developer produced events such as code commits or branch merges.
- Isolation of the components using appropriate firewall policies.
- TLS/HTTPS-enabled secure communication channels between the software components.

The core components that comprise the complete iDRIVING platform are listed below:

- **GitHub** (GitHub Inc, n.d.) (2) is a software solution that aids software teams in managing source code changes. It is an online hosting service for software development and version control. It provides distributed Git version control together with task management, continuous integration, wikis for every project, bug tracking, access control, and software feature requests. Teams of developers frequently use version control to monitor and handle changes to software code. Version control solutions, which are especially helpful for DevOps teams (3) as they can assist cut development time while boosting successful deployments with fewer disruptions and errors, allow software teams work in an agile way as development environments have increased.
- **Jenkins** (Jenkins, n.d) (4) an open-source tool automation server that supports building, deploying, and automating of the project acting as the “brain” of the process. Jenkins has been configured to respond developer related actions and triggers and initiates software build, testing and packaging as well as “pushing” images to a dedicated registry.
- **Harbor Container Registry** (5) a repository manager tool used to organize resources, it provides a private registry (Docker), where the iDRIVING artifacts are securely stored and distributed.

- **NGINX** (NGINX, 2022b) (6) an open-source web server designed as a reverse proxy. For the iDRIVING Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment services. A reverse proxy can retrieve resources from servers on behalf of a client, thus protecting the iDRIVING CI/CD platform services.
- **Keycloak** (Keycloak-Team, n.d.) (7) an open-source Identity and Access Management tool which is used to add authentication to applications and secure services. All other components of the iDRIVING CI/CD platform use the Keycloak authentication to gain access to their services. This way the users can authenticate with Keycloak rather than individual applications in centralized manner.
- **Portainer** (Portainer.io) (8) a universal container management platform that accelerates container adoption, reduces operational complexity and addresses the security challenges of running containers in Docker, Swar Nomad and Kubernetes. It is used for providing logging and health monitoring information of the developed and deployed components through a comprehensive GUI.

Figure 2 - CICD Tools Stack

Table 2 lists the URLs of the CI/CD tools that are available to the iDRIVING partners. Access to the administration interfaces of these tools is limited to the INTRA infrastructure team which also manages the underlying cloud infrastructure.

Table 2 - CICD Services URLs

Service	URL
portainer.io	https://portainer.iDriving.rid-intrasoft.eu/

Jenkins	https://jenkins.iDriving.rid-intrasoft.eu/
KEYCLOAK	https://keycloak.iDriving.rid-intrasoft.eu/
HARBOR	https://harbor.iDriving.rid-intrasoft.eu/

This set of cooperative workflows tools is established to aid with the integration process. Each individual component is presented in detail in the following subsections, and each module is accompanied by guidelines regarding its deployment.

The CI/CD Platform presented here has already been deployed and is ready to be used and tested by partners.

5.3 Basic CI/CD Workflows

The users of the CI/CD Platform will be able to connect and utilize the tools registering through their SSO account, after being redirected to the Keycloak login page as depicted in the Figure 3 below.

Figure 3 - Keycloak Login Page

The development workflow includes the subsequent phases depending on the selected approach and some security restrictions that each technical team has in regards of sharing their source code.

GitHub approach:

1. The developer commits code to the project's source code repository on GitHub.
2. A webhook between GitHub and Jenkins is enabled and initiates Jenkins's automation processes.
3. An image is created if the checks are successful and then is uploaded to the Harbor registry.
4. A webhook between Harbor and Jenkins is enabled and initiates Jenkins's deployment process.
5. The Docker image is executed and deployed on the development server through Jenkins.

Figure 4 - CI/CD: GitHub Approach

Harbor approach:

1. The developer pushes a new Docker image in Harbor Container registry.
2. A webhook between Harbor and Jenkins is enabled and initiates Jenkins's automation processes.
3. The Docker image is executed and deployed on the development server.

Figure 5 - CI/CD: Harbor Approach

A prototype project has been committed both to the code repository and to the container registry, to guide developers on how to use the above outlined stages.

5.4 CI/CD Environment – Hardware, Software and Networking

The discrete software components that make up the iDriving Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) platform are deployed on virtual servers that were made available by Hetzner Cloud, a public cloud provider. To house the iDriving testing environment, more servers are also set up (on the Hetzner cloud). The distributed and scalable nature of the CI/CD platform, allows the technical team to allocate resources optimally, ensuring operations run smoothly without encountering performance bottlenecks. Table 3 below demonstrates the status specifications of the cloud servers utilized per tool to support the development and testing activities. This table also includes some components that are already deployed on the testing servers.

Table 3 -Assets Deployment Table

Cloud Server Usage	CPUs	RAM in GBs	Storage in GBs
VPN Server	1	1	20
Harbor	2	8	80
Keycloak	2	8	80
Jenkins	2	8	80
Portainer	2	8	80
Portainer Agent	2	8	40
Kafka Broker	2	8	40
Kafka UI AKHQ	2	8	40
Kafka REST Proxy	2	8	40

The current status of the cloud servers deployed in Hetzner (9), that house all the CI/CD Tools is shown in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6 - Hetzner UI

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

The hardware details can be updated in the following integrations steps, adapting to the scaling iDriving Project needs.

The network configuration of the platform was designed to ensure a secure and smooth connection and data exchange between iDriving tools. Every server's outgoing and incoming network traffic is protected by an appropriately configured firewall; access is given to authorized partners through specific public IPs.

In addition to the configured firewall access to the testing environments is also restricted by a VPN. This VPN was deployed to enhance security in the communications between the involved partners, both within the cloud and in the field. The iDriving VPN was implemented using pfSense, which is a software is primarily used as a router and firewall software and is frequently set up as a DHCP server, DNS server, Wi-Fi access point, and VPN server, based on FreeBSD. The VPN server is deployed in a dedicated virtual machine within the cloud environment using OpenVPN distribution.

This tool exposes a user-friendly Web interface, offering an easy and comprehensive way to configure the required network settings, the VPN server, user management and client certificates. Through the dashboard, an admin can monitor the deployed network and acquire real-time insights of the traffic flow, active connections, and resource utilization. Below are depicted some details of the active VPN server.

The screenshot displays the pfSense Community Edition dashboard. The top navigation bar includes links for System, Interfaces, Firewall, Services, VPN, Status, Diagnostics, and Help. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- System Information:** A table providing details about the system, including the name (ceasefire-vpn.home.arpa), user (admin@193.192.39.19), system type (KVM Guest), BIOS vendor (Hetzner), version (2.7.0-RELEASE), CPU type (Intel Xeon Processor), and various hardware and software settings.
- Netgate Services And Support:** A section highlighting support options, including Community Support and Netgate Global Technical Assistance Center (TAC) Support. It includes a list of resources and a warning about the Netgate Device ID (NDI).
- Interfaces:** A section showing the status of network interfaces, with WAN being up and connected to a 10Gbase-T network.
- Disks:** A table showing disk usage for the root filesystem (/), with 646M used out of a 16G total size.

Figure 7 - PfSense Dashboard

Figure 8 - PfSense VPN server

5.5 CI/CD Tools

5.5.1 Git - Version Control System

Version control, also known as source control, is the practice of tracking and managing changes to software code. Version Control Systems (VCS) are software tools that help software teams manage changes to source code over time. VCS keeps track of every modification to the code in a special kind of database. It is a remote repository of files that comprise the source code of a software application. If a mistake is made, developers can compare earlier versions of the code to help fix the mistake while minimizing disruption to all team members.

GitHub is used as the VCS within the iDriving CI/CD platform. It is an easy yet powerful and intuitive git VCS. Multiple developers can concurrently create, merge, and delete parts of the code they are working independently at their local system, before applying the changes to the shared GitHub repository. GitHub offers a set of useful features to the software development process, such as version control, issue tracking, code review, wiki, etc.

For the purposes of iDriving, a dedicated organization named iDriving-Project-eu has been created, as depicted in Figure 9. Under this organization, several teams for the iDriving WPs, components and services can be created. Each partner has access to the organization to create repositories, organize users in teams and upload their source code.

Figure 9 - iDriving GitHub org - Repository Overview

Each GitHub repository should include:

- **Jenkinsfile:** A text file that contains the definition of a Jenkins Pipeline, including the steps that will be followed during the CI/CD process.
- **Dockerfile:** A text-based script of instructions that is used to create a container image.

Like every other git VCS, GitHub comes with extended branching capabilities. In most cases, there is one main branch in a repository from which each developer who works on a specific feature or bug fix creates an additional, diverging branch. Once the developers have concluded their changes on the source code, they subsequently merge their side branch back into the main branch.

5.5.2 Jenkins - Automated Build & Testing

In iDriving, Jenkins serves as the primary tool for Continuous Integration (CI) processes. CI is a main pillar of DevOps practices, automating the integration of code changes made by multiple developers into a unified software project. Jenkins facilitates this process by enabling developers to regularly push their work into a centralized repository. Once the code is integrated, Jenkins triggers automated build and test procedures to verify the accuracy and functionality of the newly added code before final integration. The typical software development workflow involving version control and CI/CD practices is described in the following points:

1. **Local Development:** Developers obtain copies of the source code locally and make modifications on their systems.

2. **Version Control:** Changes made by developers are committed to a shared, central repository, ensuring all modifications are tracked and stored centrally.
3. **Continuous Integration:** Upon new commits or changes in the central repository:
 - The server pulls the most recent version of the code to ensure it has the latest additions.
 - The application is built, and any potential issues are communicated (e.g., compilation errors, dependency conflicts).
 - Integration and unit tests are executed to check for bugs or issues in the code.
 - Artifacts (compiled code, executables, etc.) are released for testing by deploying them in a testing environment.
4. **Version Tagging:** After successful integration and testing, a tag or label is assigned to the software version built at this stage. Tags help identify specific versions of the software and aid in tracking changes and releases.

This workflow embodies the principles of continuous integration, ensuring that code changes are continuously integrated into a shared repository, tested, and deployed for further testing or use.

Furthermore, early issue detection is made possible by the previously described approach, which enables developers to promptly fix issues that arise after changes are made. Moreover, this approach (CI) is available for use for the duration of the project. Jenkins operates in a Docker container on a specialised virtual server in the Hetzner cloud for iDriving.

Jenkins's web interface is available at <https://jenkins.iDriving.rid-intrasoft.eu/>

Jenkins uses pipelines to arrange tasks, actions, and events into a coherent sequence. Software development, testing, packaging, deployment, and storage are all included in these tasks. The iDriving GitHub organization's repositories are connected to corresponding Jenkins Pipeline jobs through particular Jenkins folders. The analogous repository process is initiated by commits, merges, and other source code modifications in Git repositories. The pipeline, in turn, defines the build, test, and compilation phases.

Jenkins deployment methods are made possible by two strategies that are specified in the iDriving CI/CD flow. In one, webhooks are used to facilitate communication between Jenkins and Harbor, while in the other, webhooks are necessary to integrate Jenkins with GitHub. The Jenkins file that sets up the pipeline defines the chosen strategy.

For the constructed Jenkins folders, a role-based access control system is set up, limiting access to only authorised members of the associated component owner's

technical team. The Jenkins folders made for each iDriving tool to facilitate and carry out its automatic deployment are displayed in Figure 10 below.

Figure 10 - Jenkins UI

A Jenkinsfile is used to define the Jenkins pipelines. The Jenkins pipeline is a perfectly organised series of stages for building, testing, and deploying applications. It implements a simple three-stage continuous delivery methodology. With each new build trigger, the Jenkins server can pull the most recent version of the Jenkinsfile. A sample Jenkinsfile is presented below.

```
pipeline {
  agent any
  environment {
    APP_NAME = "Dummyrest"
    MAJOR_RELEASE = 0.1
    DOCKER_TAG = ":0.1.${env.BUILD_NUMBER}"
    DOCKER_REG = "harbor.iDriving.rid-intrasoft.eu"
    DOCKER_REPO = "/iDriving/"
    DOCKER_REG_CREDS = "harbor-jenkins-creds"
  }
  stages {
    // *** IMAGE BUILD STAGE ***
    stage("Build_Docker_Images"){
      steps {
        sh 'DOCKER_TAG=test docker compose build'
      }
    }
    // *** Functional & Integration Tests ***
    stage("Test_the_image"){
      steps {
        sh 'DOCKER_TAG=test docker compose up -d'
        sh 'bash jenkins/tests/func_test.sh ${HOST_URL}'
        sh 'DOCKER_TAG=test docker compose down --rmi all'
      }
    }
  }
}
```

```
// *** Push Images In Harbor ***
stage("Push_Image"){
  when {
    environment name: "GIT_BRANCH", value: "origin/master"
  }
  steps {
    withCredentials([[class: 'UsernamePasswordMultiBinding', credentialsId: 'harbor-jenkins-creds',
usernameVariable: 'USERNAME', passwordVariable: 'PASSWORD']]){
      sh 'docker compose build'
      sh 'docker login ${DOCKER_REG} -u ${USERNAME} -p ${PASSWORD}'
      sh 'docker image push ${DOCKER_REG}${DOCKER_REPO}rid-dummyrest${DOCKER_TAG}'
      sh 'DOCKER_TAG=":latest" docker compose build'
      sh 'docker image push ${DOCKER_REG}${DOCKER_REPO}rid-dummyrest:latest'
    }
  }
}

// *** Deploy ***
stage("Deployment"){
  when {
    environment name: "GIT_BRANCH", value: "origin/master"
  }
  steps {
    withCredentials([[class: 'UsernamePasswordMultiBinding', credentialsId: 'harbor-jenkins-creds',
usernameVariable: 'USERNAME', passwordVariable: 'PASSWORD']]){
      sh 'docker login ${DOCKER_REG} -u ${USERNAME} -p ${PASSWORD}'
      sh 'docker compose pull'
      sh 'docker compose up -d'
      sh 'docker ps'
    }
  }
}
}
```

Figure 11 - Sample Jenkinsfile

The various stages of deployment that can be identified are illustrated in and below. The procedure consists of a deployment pipeline that places the tools in the operational environment, a testing pipeline that runs the application in the testing environment, and a kill pipeline that ends the deployment while it is in progress. To ensure optimal workflow, certain processes are set and automatically carried out.

Figure 12 - Jenkins - Demo Pipeline Folder Structure

Figure 13 - Jenkins - Demo Pipeline Execution History

5.5.3 Portainer - Monitoring

As an open-source and lightweight software platform, Portainer is used in managing and handling Docker containers. This adaptable tool simplifies several containerized application management tasks. It performs exceptionally well when it comes to monitoring, debugging, and deploying containerized apps. Within the framework of iDriving, Portainer is essential in giving a summary of the apps that are operating on cloud servers in containerized packaging. Moreover, it facilitates the expedited identification and resolution of problems that can emerge while these containerized apps are in use. With its broad capabilities and easy-to-use interface, Portainer is a valuable tool for managing containerized workloads in cloud environments.

The web interface of Portainer can be found at <https://portainer.iDriving.rid-intrasoft.eu/> and an overview of the tool is depicted in Figure 14 and in Figure 15 below.

Figure 14 - Portainer Environment's Overview

Figure 15 - Portainer - Environment Containers details

5.5.4 Harbor - Private Container Registry

Harbor is an open-source registry created to guarantee the security and reliability of container images. The purpose of this tool is to support engineers in reliably and securely managing artifacts across cloud-native computing platforms such as Docker and Kubernetes. Harbor is a Cloud Native Computing Foundation (CNCF) graduated project. It has capabilities like role-based access control and policy implementation to protect artifacts, image marking as trusted, and docker image inspection to find and fix flaws. It also provides an extensive set of tools and features covering interoperability, performance optimisation, and compliance. Because of this, Harbor is an invaluable resource for businesses and individuals using containerized applications since it enables them to meet crucial operational and security needs. This tool works as the repository for storing the application artifacts within the framework of iDriving. Moreover, it is essential in starting the automation process that deploys every module in the project.

The web interface of Harbor can be found at <https://harbor.iDriving.rid-intrasoft.eu/>

Specialised artifact repositories inside Harbor have been established in accordance with the data collected from the activities conducted within WP3, where the technical components are being built. Each one of these project repositories is specifically assigned to a certain module and serves as a central location to store the Docker images associated with that specific component. The development and deployment processes are streamlined by this well-organized structure, which also makes sure that each component's Docker images are effectively saved and available within the Harbor platform. It also makes managing and deploying module-specific artifacts easier. The created repositories per module are depicted in Figure 16 below.

Figure 16 - Harbor UI

5.5.5 Keycloak

Keycloak is an open-source Identity and Access Management (IAM) tool. It streamlines the authentication process for applications and IT services. Keycloak offers a broad set of features, like SSO, authentication and authorization, social login, multifactor authentication, and centralised user management. The purpose of Keycloak is to ensure that the right people in an organization have appropriate access to resources. Keycloak is an open-source tool having a license with an Apache License 2.0. With Keycloak, you can secure services with a minimum of time and add authentication to applications.

In iDriving CI/CD Keycloak acts as the SSO point for most of the tools with the only exception being GitHub. By using Keycloak there is no need to manage and create user accounts to each tool but centrally controlling and issuing user groups and access details. A specific domain for the iDriving project was created and two kinds of users, one being the administrators from INTRA and the other the users of the iDriving CI/CD.

The Web interface of Keycloak can be found at <https://keycloak.iDriving.rid-intrasoft.eu/> and it is shown in Figure 17 below.

Figure 17 - Keycloak Admin Console UI

5.5.6 NGINX – Reverse Proxy

NGINX is used on top of the iDriving CI/CD infrastructure as a reverse proxy. A reverse proxy is a proxy server that is set up between the firewall and the back-end servers in a private network. Its job is to try to keep network traffic flowing between clients and servers by forwarding and redirecting client requests (from a web browser, for example) to the proper back-end location.

The deployed CI/CD stack services, including the Container Registry, and the CI server, are situated behind NGINX servers along with, letsencrypt-proxy-companion instances that are responsible for automatically configuring the nginx proxy servers.

```
Version: '3.7'
services:
  nginx-proxy:
    image: jwilder/nginx-proxy:alpine
    container_name: nginx-proxy
    ports:
      - "443:443"
      - 80:80
    volumes:
      - /var/run/docker.sock:/tmp/docker.sock:ro
      - letsencrypt-certs:/etc/nginx/certs
      - letsencrypt-vhost-d:/etc/nginx/vhost.d
      - letsencrypt-html:/usr/share/nginx/html
      - ./client_max_body_size.conf:/etc/nginx/conf.d/client_max_body_size.conf:ro
    networks:
      - "proxy-network"

  letsencrypt-proxy:
    image: jrcs/letsencrypt-nginx-proxy-companion:stable
    container_name: letsencrypt-proxy
    volumes:
      - /var/run/docker.sock:/var/run/docker.sock:ro
      - letsencrypt-certs:/etc/nginx/certs
      - letsencrypt-vhost-d:/etc/nginx/vhost.d
      - letsencrypt-html:/usr/share/nginx/html
    environment:
      - DEFAULT_EMAIL=${LETSencrypt_EMAIL}
      - NGINX_PROXY_CONTAINER=nginx-proxy
    networks:
      - "proxy-network"

networks:
  proxy-network:
    name: proxy-network
    driver: bridge

volumes:
  letsencrypt-certs:
  letsencrypt-vhost-d:
  letsencrypt-html:
```

Figure 18 - NGINX - Docker-Compose file

5.5.7 Certificates Management

By enabling SSL connection and instructing user browsers to connect through HTTPS to the CI/CD services, data transmission security and service identification are achieved to and from the CI/CD services. For this, Let's Encrypt (Let's Encrypt, n.d) certificates have been implemented. The public can utilize free certificates from Let's Encrypt, a non-profit certificate authority (CA). It is a trustworthy, free certificate that offers automatic renewal. Moreover, Let's Encrypt acts as a platform using cutting-edge security methods. Finally, the letsencrypt-nginx-proxy module is utilized, which enables Let's Encrypt certificates for the NGINX proxy container to be generated and renewed automatically.

This approach ensures compliance with established security policies and maintains a robust security posture for the CI/CD environment.

6 iDriving Message Bus – Apache Kafka

The following section provides an overview of the Apache Kafka based message bus implemented within iDriving. Apache Kafka forms the backbone of inter-component communication, enabling message exchange among the diverse systems comprising the iDriving ecosystem. This infrastructure supports robust real-time data flows, ensuring all modules can seamlessly interact through standardized messaging protocols. The details presented herein encompass the Kafka setup, operational interfaces, and available APIs, designed explicitly for secure and streamlined access within the project.

6.1 Apache Kafka Setup

The Kafka setup within iDriving has been deployed utilizing Docker containers orchestrated within a dedicated infrastructure, ensuring optimal scalability, maintainability, and ease of operation. To facilitate secure communication and resource access, all Kafka components are accessible exclusively through the iDriving VPN service, provisioned via a dedicated pfSense VPN profile.

The deployed Kafka services include:

- **Kafka Broker:** Serving as the backbone message handler, managing topics, partitions, and overall message distribution.
- **Kafka REST Proxy:** Offering an HTTP-based interface for Kafka, providing simplified API-based interactions.
- **AKHQ (Apache Kafka HQ):** A comprehensive GUI-based tool to manage and monitor Kafka clusters visually.
- **Swagger UI:** An interactive API documentation tool providing detailed descriptions, examples, and test capabilities for Kafka REST Proxy endpoints, facilitating easy integration and testing.

The specific Docker containers deployed, their corresponding IP addresses, and service ports are illustrated below:

Container	IP	Port	Status
iDriving-kafka	1**.**.**.**8	9092	Deployed
iDriving-kafka-rest-proxy	1**.**.**.**8	8082	Deployed
iDriving-akhq	1**.**.**.**8	8081	Deployed
iDriving-swagger-ui	1**.**.**.**8	8083	Deployed

6.1.1 AKHQ User Interface

The Apache Kafka HQ (AKHQ) provides a user-friendly graphical interface allowing developers and system administrators to manage Kafka clusters efficiently. AKHQ facilitates tasks such as topic inspection, message browsing, consumer group monitoring, and topic management, thus simplifying operations within the Kafka environment.

AKHQ is accessible through iDriving VPN only.

Figure 19 - AKHQ Web Interface

6.2 Apache Kafka API Proxy

The Kafka API Proxy has been deployed to simplify integration for components requiring HTTP-based interaction with Kafka. Using the Kafka REST Proxy (based on Confluent’s Kafka REST Proxy), developers can produce and consume messages, manage Kafka topics, and access cluster metadata without directly interacting with Kafka clients.

This approach significantly simplifies development tasks and integration efforts, allowing for standard RESTful HTTP interactions instead of traditional Kafka consumer-producer patterns, when needed. The API Proxy is securely integrated within the Kafka stack and accessible via VPN-secured HTTP endpoints.

6.2.1 Endpoint Documentation – Swagger UI

The API endpoints provided by the Kafka REST Proxy are thoroughly documented using Swagger UI, offering an interactive platform for exploration, testing, and validation of API calls. This allows seamless onboarding for developers and facilitates debugging and integration activities.

Swagger UI documentation for the Kafka REST API Proxy is accessible through iDriving VPN only.

Figure 20 - Swagger UI Web Interface part 1

Figure 21 - Swagger UI Web Interface part 2

7 Conclusion / Future Work

This deliverable has presented and analysed the integration framework of iDriving, with particular focus on the specification and mapping of system interfaces, the documentation of information flows between components, and the deployment views that capture the distribution of components across the project infrastructure. The integration plan, including its phases, methodologies, and execution steps, has been comprehensively described, providing clear guidance for the progressive development and validation of all project components.

In addition, the deliverable has detailed the CI/CD infrastructure supporting the development lifecycle, including the description and implementation of continuous integration and deployment pipelines, the underlying tools and services, and the DevOps methodologies adopted. The roles and readiness of all major software components have been documented, ensuring transparency regarding the current state of the first prototype.

While the integration activities described in this deliverable provide a solid foundation for the first iDriving prototype, several risks and limitations remain before full-scale deployment. Certain components and interfaces are still under active development, which may introduce unforeseen interoperability issues or require further alignment of data formats and protocols as the project progresses. Additionally, real-world pilot environments may present operational challenges not fully replicable in testbed conditions. The CI/CD infrastructure, though robust, depends on the availability and reliability of underlying cloud services and secure VPN access, which could impact continuity in case of outages or security incidents. Finally, timely updates and contributions from all project partners are essential to ensure full readiness and mitigate potential delays. These risks will be closely monitored, and contingency measures will be taken as the project advances towards subsequent prototype releases.

The integration plan and infrastructure established in this deliverable will guide the subsequent implementation, testing, and validation activities. Future deliverables, namely D5.4 and D5.5, will provide updated insights into the evolving prototype, detailing advancements in development, integration, and deployment, as well as incorporating refinements that emerge throughout the next phases of the project lifecycle.

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9 Annexes

9.1 Annex 1. Integration Matrix

Each component is identified by its ID as defined in Section **Error! Reference source not found.** This matrix provides a high-level overview of the interface specification tables of section 3.1, which detail each interface individually.

Component	IC1		IC2		IC3		IC4		IC5		IC6		IC7		IC8		IC9		IC10		IC11		IC12		IC13		IC14		IC15							
	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface						
IC1							↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↔	RestAPI	↔	RestAPI																				
IC2																																				
IC3																																				
IC4	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC5	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC6	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC7	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC8	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC9	↕	Apache kafka																																		
IC10	↕	Apache kafka																																		
IC11	↕	Apache kafka																																		
IC12	↕	Apache kafka																																		
IC13	↕	Apache kafka																																		
IC14	↕	Apache kafka																																		
IC15	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC16	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC17	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC18	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC19	↕	Apache kafka																																		
IC20	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC21	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC22	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC23	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC24	↕	RestAPI	↕	other	↕	other	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI																								
IC25	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC26	↕	RestAPI																																		
IC26.1	↕																																			
IC26.2	↕																																			
IC26.3	↕																																			
IC27	↕	RestAPI																																		

Figure 22 - Integration matrix part 1

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Component	IC16		IC17		IC18		IC19		IC20		IC21		IC22		IC23		IC24		IC25		IC26		IC26.1		IC26.2		IC26.3		IC27	
	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface	Data Flow Direction	Interface								
IC1	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI									↕	RestAPI
IC2															↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI										
IC3															↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI										
IC4									☑	RestAPI	☑	RestAPI			↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI									↕	RestAPI
IC5									☑	RestAPI	☑	RestAPI			↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI	↕	RestAPI									↕	RestAPI
IC6	☑	Apache kafka	☑	Apache kafka			☑	Apache kafka					☑	Apache kafka															☑	RestAPI
IC7																														
IC8														☑	Apache kafka															
IC9														☑	Apache kafka															
IC10	☑	Apache kafka																												
IC11																														
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IC26																														
IC26.1																														
IC26.2																														
IC26.3																														
IC27																														

Figure 23 - Integration matrix part 2

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles
Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/07/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01 **Total cost:** € 4,998,733.75 **Coordinator:** Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH)

iDriving Consortium

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